

RAISING INTERNET FREEDOM TO A NEW LEVEL IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article analyzes the indicators of Uzbekistan's internet freedom in international rankings. In the modern world, freedom of internet usage is a global problem.

Keywords: internet, information, cyber security, communication, technology, freedom.

In today's modern world, how the rights of people, especially young people, to freedom of thought and speech, to search for, receive and distribute the information they want, directly depends on their free use of information resources, communication technologies, in particular, the Internet. In our national legislation, norms related to information security and cyber security issues are being systematically improved in parallel with the development of information technologies. The new constitution guaranteed the right to freely use the Internet. That is, "Everyone has the right to freedom of thought, speech and belief." Everyone has the right to seek, receive and impart information. The state creates conditions for ensuring the use of the Internet global information network. Restrictions on the right to seek, receive and distribute information are limited only in accordance with the law and only for the protection of the constitutional system, public health, social morality, rights and freedoms of other persons, public safety and public order, as well as state secrets or it is allowed in the scope necessary to prevent the disclosure of other secrets protected by law." [1]

includes the ability for users to determine their own views on information on the Internet, use dating services, share opinions with others, and express their opinions.

Such freedom also does not permit the collection of data by external distributors on the Internet, control of user activities and other personal data, not to be used for the purpose of changing other people during the restriction, to ensure personal protection and to carry out other practices, and It is required to be informed about personal data directly, more deeply and accurately.

Internet access has improved in Uzbekistan in recent years. Internet access is still primarily based on asymmetric digital subscriber line (ADSL) technology. According to the Economist Impact's Inclusive Internet Index 2022, 93.6 percent of households have access to the Internet.[2] According to the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), overall Internet penetration is 76.6 percent as of 2021. [3] In 2022, the level of fixed internet subscription in the country was 26 percent, and the level of active penetration of mobile broadband connection was 104 percent.[4]

Internet connection speed remains relatively low. Subscribers face poor connection quality and frequent interruptions. According to Ookla's Speedtest Global Index, as of May 2023, the average landline broadband download speed was 49.69 Megabits per second (Mbps), while the average mobile broadband download speed was It was 19.61. [5] Uztelecom, which is considered a state monopoly in the field of telecommunications, increased the capacity of Uzbekistan's international internet channels by 3.2 terabits per second (Tbit/s) in 2022. However, users regularly experience lower than reported speeds and even outages.

Mobile contact providers second generation 2 G , 3 G and 4G _ services present they reach , of the population most are 2G (99 percent) , 3 G (90 percent) and 4 G (66 percent) networks with cover taken .[6]

State-owned Uztelekom and several mobile service providers offer public Wi-Fi hotspots in limited areas. In February 2018, President Sh. Mirziyoyev signed a decree on the introduction of tax incentives and advertising rights for business entities investing in Wi-Fi hotspots. - announced that it has installed Wi-Fi hotspots, with a total of 3,450 Wi-Fi hotspots across the country.

In Uzbekistan, the price of internet access continues to decrease relative to household income. However, there are significant geographic and gender differences.

In 2022, ITU (International electrical connection union) reported that 5 gigabytes of fixed broadband would account for 1.71 percent of gross national income per capita, and 2 gigabytes of mobile broadband would account for 85 percent of GDP per capita.[7]

Outside of Tashkent, the level of internet access is very low. The capital has the highest rate of Internet access and fiber-to-the-premises (FTTB) broadband in Uzbekistan, which is much higher than the country's 12 regions and the Republic of Karakalpakstan. In addition, information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructure depends on a stable electricity supply, which is lacking in some rural areas.

As shown in the coverage maps of national ISPs, there are still very few high-speed FTTB connections in residential areas outside of Tashkent. In April 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev issued a decree that all settlements will be provided with high-speed Internet by 2021, after which the Internet speed has increased significantly in many areas.

According to the Economist Impact's Inclusive Internet Index 2022, men access the internet more than women, and there is a 13.3 percent gap between their internet access rates. The difference in mobile communication is relatively lower, 9.6 percent.[8]

In July 2021, the State Inspectorate for Supervision in the field of Information and Telecommunications of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Uzkomnzorot) fined

Skype, Twitter, TikTok, VKontakte and WeChat for violating the new amendments to the Personal Data Law. restricted access (see B1 and C6).[9] On November 3, 2021, additional social media platforms and messaging apps, including Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, Odnoklassniki, Telegram, and YouTube, were blocked, but access was restored on the same day (see B1). In August 2022, the Information and Media Agency (AIMK) announced that Twitter, VKontakte and WeChat had been unblocked and that the government was in talks with TikTok to unblock the app. Although TikTok has been blocked since 2021, users have been able to access the app briefly at various times since the initial blocking order .[10]

The online media environment in Uzbekistan is developing, and there is evidence that registered media outlets are beginning to cover politically and socially sensitive topics. Compared to previous years, more Internet users are reading and engaging with news from independent sites.

Facebook and Telegram users can follow daily discussions on political, economic, and social issues in groups such as "Reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan: Solutions and Challenges." [11] In some cases, online activism can lead to real-world change. For example, in February 2021, the mayor of Tashkent promised not to cut trees in the central park. After campaigning on Facebook, residents took action to save it. Citizens are making extensive use of the government's 'virtual office' initiative, as well as the government's official petition platform, My Opinion, to speak directly to government officials.

Internet freedom is granted to people in order to ensure a set of rights and opportunities provided by states, enterprises and networks. This includes providing users with the freedom to learn how to use data collection, express opinions, use dating services, and a number of other basic activities.

Internet freedom gives people the following rights:

1. Expressing Your Opinions: Users have the freedom to express their opinions and mention themselves on social media through the Internet.

2. Information sharing: Users can access international and other information through the Internet.

3. Dating and Communication: The Internet allows people to meet, communicate and connect with each other around the world.

4. Compliance and Marketing: Selling, marketing and advertising the services and products of individual or corporate organizations over the Internet.

5. Organization of events: they leave their comments on the events they saw through the Internet, events, indicators, temporary sites.

These freedoms are limited by certain guidelines set by states and businesses. Internet freedom plays a major role in providing important opportunities for people to communicate, obtain information, learn and conduct activities.

We offer the following suggestions and recommendations to ensure Internet freedom :

1. Protect with a password: Using a strong password and using a combination of letters, numbers, and symbols to make it strong increases your freedom.

2. Second verification: You can increase your freedom by enabling the second verification when accessing one of the online services you use.

3. Protection of personal data: Use your personal data only where necessary and of course protect it adequately.

4. Protection from advertising and cookies: You can protect your personal networks by managing cookies and advertising in your browser.

5. n protection on social networks : Increases your freedom to continuously contribute and adjust privacy on social networks to avoid theft of your personal information.

6. Use security software: Use antivirus and security software, keep them up-to-date, and keep your software and browser safe.

7. Messages and email security: Do not open unknown preferences, do not open unknown email messages. Use reliable sources when communicating your messages.

8. Be careful when sharing information: When finding information on the Internet, first check the sources that provide the information and verify the messages from those sources.

9. Use consistent guides: A guide can help you set your privacy and stay safe online.

These suggestions can help increase internet freedom for users. Each user should take appropriate precautions to ensure their own security and privacy.

The bottom line is that the freedom to use the Internet without conflicting with the law and its effective use remains the need of the hour. When using the Internet, our young people must first of all contribute to the development of society through personal development.

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